

BONE GRAFT AND ITS USE IN DENTISTRY: AN INTEGRATIVE REVIEW

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Enxerto ósseo e seu uso na odontologia: Revisão integrativa da literatura

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REVISÃO DE LITERATURA

ABSTRACT

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Objective: This study aimed to analyze, through an integrative review of the literature, the scientific evidence on the use of bone grafts in dentistry, addressing its clinical indications, types of grafts, applications and therapeutic results. **Methods:** An integrative literature review was conducted in the PubMed, SciELO, and Google Scholar databases, covering the period from 2010 to 2024, with no language restrictions. Original articles, reviews, and case reports addressing the use of autogenous, allogenic, xenogenic, and synthetic bone grafts in implant dentistry were included. After screening and applying inclusion and exclusion criteria, 13 studies were selected for qualitative analysis. **Results:** Autogenous grafts are considered the gold standard due to their high biocompatibility and osteogenic potential, with success rates above 90%. Allogenic and xenogenic grafts serve as viable alternatives when autologous bone is limited, while alloplastic materials offer benefits such as availability and elimination of donor site morbidity. Guided Bone Regeneration (GBR) techniques and the use of biomaterials combined with membranes and growth factors expand therapeutic possibilities, enhancing predictability and clinical success in implant dentistry. **Conclusion:** The selection of the graft type must be individualized according to the patient's clinical condition, the extent of bone deficiency, and the rehabilitation goals. Continuous advances in biomaterials and regenerative techniques improve treatment predictability, safety, and long-term implant success, reinforcing the essential role of bone grafting in contemporary dentistry.

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Keywords: Biomaterials, Bone graft, Bone regeneration, Dental implantology, Oral rehabilitation

RESUMO **Objetivo:** Este estudo teve como objetivo analisar, por meio de uma revisão integrativa da literatura, as evidências científicas sobre o uso de enxertos ósseos na odontologia, abordando suas indicações clínicas, tipos de enxertos, aplicações e resultados terapêuticos. **Métodos:** Foi conduzida uma revisão integrativa da literatura nas bases de dados PubMed, SciELO e Google Scholar, abrangendo o período de 2010 a 2024. Utilizaram-se os descritores “enxerto ósseo”, “implantodontia”, “regeneração óssea”, “biomateriais” e “reabilitação oral”, combinados com operadores booleanos “AND” e “OR”. Foram incluídos artigos originais, revisões e relatos de caso que abordassem os diferentes tipos de enxertos (autógeno, alógeno, xenógeno e sintético) aplicados à implantodontia, excluindo-se teses, dissertações, capítulos de livros e estudos em animais. Após a triagem e exclusão de duplicatas, 13 artigos preencheram os critérios e foram analisados descritivamente. **Resultados:** Os enxertos autógenos são considerados o padrão-ouro devido à sua alta biocompatibilidade e potencial osteogênico, apresentando taxas de sucesso superiores a 90%. Os enxertos alógenos e xenógenos constituem alternativas viáveis quando a disponibilidade de osso autógeno é limitada, enquanto os materiais aloplásticos oferecem vantagens como ampla disponibilidade e ausência de morbidade da área doadora. As técnicas de Regeneração Óssea Guiada (GBR) e o uso de biomateriais associados a membranas e fatores de crescimento ampliam as possibilidades terapêuticas, aumentando a previsibilidade e o sucesso clínico na implantodontia. **Conclusão:** A escolha do tipo de enxerto deve ser individualizada, considerando o quadro clínico, a extensão do defeito ósseo e os objetivos reabilitadores. A constante evolução dos biomateriais e das técnicas regenerativas contribui para o aumento da previsibilidade, segurança e longevidade dos implantes dentários, reforçando o papel essencial dos enxertos ósseos na odontologia contemporânea.

Palavras-chave: Biomateriais, Enxerto ósseo, Implantodontia, Reabilitação oral, Regeneração óssea.

INTRODUCTION

Bone grafting, also known as bone augmentation, is a surgical procedure that replaces lost bone with osteogenic-inducing material, which can be derived from the patient (autogenous), from an artificial or synthetic substitute (alloplastic), or from another living being (allogeneic). It involves the insertion of bone material into areas that are deficient from an anatomical or functional perspective.¹ This procedure is used in treatments such as maxillary sinus augmentation, grafts in dental cavities, or alveolar ridge augmentation. Bone tissue could fully regenerate when there is appropriate space for its growth, which allows the newly formed bone to completely replace the graft material at the end of the procedure. Bone graft materials vary according to their origin. Autogenous grafts are taken from the patient's own body, such as the iliac crest, maxilla, or mandible, and go through three phases of healing: osteogenesis, Osteoinduction and osteoconduction, where the native bone replaces the graft material. Allogeneic grafts, on the other hand, come from donors of the same species and are processed and stored in bone banks.^{1,2}

They aid in bone formation mainly through osteoinduction and osteoconduction, but they do not have osteogenesis because their cells are not viable. Moreover, it is essential to ensure that the donor's medical history is free of conditions that could affect the recipient. Alloplasts, on the other hand, are synthetic materials; for example, we have bioactive ceramics such as calcium phosphates. These materials promote bone formation through osteoconduction and can be mixed with growth factors to improve bone density. The particle size and porosity of these materials affect their resorption rate, with larger particles remaining longer at the graft site and more porous materials being resorbed more quickly. Still regarding grafts, there are xenogeneic implants, Materials derived from porcine or bovine sources are less common but have shown success when properly indicated, especially due to their similarity to human cancellous bone. Although these materials show good incorporation into the remaining human bone, the effectiveness of methods for inactivating the BSE prion is always a concern.³

This study aimed to analyze, through an integrative review of the literature, the scientific evidence on the use of bone grafts in dentistry, addressing its clinical indications, types of grafts, applications and therapeutic results.

OBJECTIVE

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PRISMA FLOWCHART

An integrative literature review was conducted following the method proposed by Whitemore and Knafl (2005) with the objective of gathering and analyzing scientific publications related to the use of bone grafts in dentistry. The search was carried out in the PubMed, SciELO, and Google Scholar databases, covering the period from January 2010 to 2024 with no language restriction. The descriptors (DeCS/MeSH) used were bone graft, dental implantology, bone regeneration, biomaterials, and oral rehabilitation. The search strategy used Boolean operators "AND" and "OR" to cross the terms, resulting in: ("Bone graft" OR "Bone graft") AND ("Implantology" OR "Dental Implantology") AND ("Bone regeneration" OR "Bone regeneration").

Exclusion criteria were selected from original articles, literature reviews, and case reports between 2010 and 2024; Studies involving human beings; Studies that addressed types of grafts (autogenous, xenogenic, allogeneic or synthetic) and their application in implantology.

The exclusion criteria were: Duplicate jobs between databases; articles that do not have a direct relationship with the proposed theme. The selection and screening of articles followed the adapted PRISMA model (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Initially, 120 articles were identified (PubMed = 54; SciELO = 23; Google Scholar = 43). After removing duplicates (n = 32) and excluding studies that did not meet the inclusion criteria (n = 60), 13 articles were included in the final analysis (Figura 1).

Figure 1 – PRISMA flowchart of the literature search and study selection process.

Bone tissue

Bone is a mineralized connective tissue that performs several essential physiological functions, such as the storage of minerals, the locomotion of the limbs, the support and protection of organs and soft tissues,

the regulation of pH, and the uptake of toxic metals, such as lead. In addition, it provides the right environment for the bone marrow, which is responsible for the production of blood cells.¹

The homeostasis of the skeletal system depends on a balance between the processes of bone formation and resorption, which result from the dynamic interaction between osteoblasts — boneforming cells — and osteoclasts, responsible for resorption. This coordinated activity is tightly controlled by local and systemic factors, including the immune system. When osteoclastic activity predominates, pathological resorption may occur, observed in conditions such as periodontitis, rheumatoid arthritis and osteoporosis.^{2,3}

A detailed understanding of this process is critical for the development of therapeutic protocols aimed at restoring the balance of bone remodeling. Thus, in this review, aspects related to the chemical composition of the bone matrix, the main cells involved, the remodeling process, and local and systemic factors, such as cytokines and hormones, that interfere with this mechanism, are addressed.^{1,2,3}

Bone tissue regeneration

The bone regeneration process is based on three fundamental mechanisms that act in a complementary way: osteogenesis, osteoinduction and osteoconduction. Osteoinduction is the process by which the recruitment of immature mesenchymal cells occurs, which are stimulated to differentiate into pre-osteoblasts, which, once matured, become active osteoblasts responsible for the formation of the organic bone matrix and mineralization through the deposition of calcium phosphate. In fracture situations, bone regeneration strongly depends on osteoinduction, while osteoconduction is the phenomenon observed when bone growth occurs on a conductive surface or structure, as in dental implants.^{1,2}

Techniques based on these principles, such as Guided Bone Regeneration (GBR), have been widely employed in combination with bone grafts and titanium implants. The method uses biological or synthetic membranes that prevent soft tissue invasion and favor bone growth in the underlying bone defect. Recent studies highlight that the porosity and composition of membranes directly influence cell behavior and regeneration efficiency, and that the optimization of biomaterials is essential for the improvement of this technique.^{3,4}

From a biological point of view, understanding the cellular and molecular events involved in bone regeneration is essential to correlate local and systemic factors that affect the process. Experimental studies have shown that the use of barrier membranes is able to guide bone formation and maturation in mandibular defects, reproducing stages of intramembranous formation. Currently, it is understood that bone regeneration depends on the interaction of osteoprogenitor and immunological cells, adequate support (blood clot), signaling molecules, in addition to vascular supply and mechanical stability, which allow the conversion of immature bone into mature lamellar bone.³

Types of grafts

With the advancement of technologies and research in biomaterials, several types of bone grafts have emerged. The autogenous graft is considered the gold standard, due to its high osteoconductivity and biocompatibility, since the material is removed from the patient himself, eliminating the risk of rejection. These grafts contain viable bone cells, growth factors, and extracellular matrix, promoting effective and predictable bone regeneration.^{1,2}

Allogeneic grafts, obtained from donors of the same species, have been associated with higher failure rates due to possible immunological reactions. However, recent reviews indicate that its clinical effectiveness is comparable to that of autogenous grafts, especially in adult patients, although there are still risks of rejection and viral transmission.^{5,6}

On the other hand, xenogenic grafts, derived from tissues of other species, have gained popularity in regenerative dentistry, standing out for their osteoconductive capacity and good clinical results. Despite concerns about compatibility and immunogenicity, they constitute a viable alternative when there is insufficient autologous bone available.^{3,5,7}

Brazilian studies also describe the evolution of grafting materials and techniques, emphasizing their importance in oral rehabilitation and in the choice of the type of graft according to the bone defect.⁸ In addition, Brazilian studies point to the profile of the use of these materials among dentists, highlighting that the choice of the type of graft is directly related to professional experience and the availability of biomaterials.⁹

Classification

It is possible to classify bone grafts according to their origin: autogenous, obtained from the patient himself; allogeneic, coming from another individual of the same species; xenogens, derived from tissues of different species, such as bovine or porcine; and alloplastics, produced by laboratory synthesis from bioactive materials. This classification is widely accepted in the literature and supports the choice of the most appropriate type of graft in each clinical situation.³

Bone grafts can also be classified according to the surgical technique employed, and the bone can be removed all together or particulate (ground), depending on the clinical need and the extent of the defect.^{2,3}

In addition, as for the form of presentation and structure, the graft can be: Cortical, formed by denser and more rigid bone, usually obtained from the iliac crest, offering good initial stability.

Spongy, consisting of highly vascularized and less dense tissue, favoring revascularization and healing. Compound, a combination of cortical and spongy types, which optimizes bone regeneration and associates mechanical resistance with better biological integration^{1,5}

Features

It is possible to characterize grafts according to their biological quality, and those with greater biocompatibility and vascularization are recommended. Autogenous grafting is considered the gold standard, as it brings together high osteogenic, osteoinductive and osteoconductive potential. However, the choice of graft type must balance predictability, surgical time, and cost, and allogeneic grafts may represent an effective alternative in specific situations.¹

Autogenous graft

Considered the best type of graft, the material is taken from the host that will receive it, with the mandible being one of the main places of obtainment.

Because it contains growth factors that stimulate the proliferation and differentiation of osteoprogenitor cells into osteoblasts, and due to its high osteoconductive, osteoinductive and osteogenic potential, the autogenous graft is considered the gold standard in bone reconstruction, with success rates of more than 90% in different types of defects.^{1,2}

The quality and quantity of bone tissue generated in the area are also determining factors for the success of the treatment. Autogenous grafting is highly effective due to the biocompatibility between the donor and recipient sites, promoting rapid osteoconduction, osteogenesis, and revascularization, which reduces the risk of infections. However, in extensive defects, the surgery must be performed in a hospital environment, under general anesthesia and with a multidisciplinary team, which implies greater complexity and cost.^{2,10}

Allogeneic graft

At the beginning of the twentieth century, the first procedures involving allogeneic implants in medicine had limited success rates, close to 50%. In recent decades, these grafts have become widely used in dentistry, since they eliminate the morbidity of the donor site and reduce surgical time and operative costs, representing an effective alternative when there is a need for large bone volumes.^{9,10} Although allogeneic grafts are often associated with a higher failure rate due to the possibility of an immune reaction of the recipient, recent studies have demonstrated clinical results like those obtained with autogenous grafts, especially in adult patients.⁹

Despite this, allogeneic grafting still has limitations in relation to the ideal characteristics of bone regeneration. Its matrix acts as a natural osteoconductive structure, allowing fibrovascular infiltration, cell attraction, and formation of new bone tissue, although with lower osteoinductive potential compared to the autogenous one.^{5,10}

Xenogeneic graft

Derivatives from broad sources can lead to immune rejection and present a risk of viral transmission. Xenogenic grafting, widely used in dentistry, functions predominantly as an osteoconductive material and has been shown to be effective in several clinical applications.³ Despite their widespread adoption, there are still concerns about the biological safety of bovine grafts, due to the theoretical possibility of transmission of prions associated with bovine spongiform encephalopathy (BSE). Studies indicate that alkaline treatment and deproteinization performed during the processing of biomaterials such as Bio-Oss®, a classic example of xenogenous grafting, significantly reduce this risk, although there is still no complete consensus on the efficacy of total inactivation of prions.^{3,5}

Another type of biomaterial of animal origin under study is chitosan, extracted from the exoskeleton of arthropods. When associated with compounds such as phosphoric ester, it forms a hybrid alloplastic material with osteoconductive potential and cytocompatible properties. Recent research indicates promising results regarding the biocompatibility and safety of this compound, making it a viable alternative for bone grafting applications.^{10,11}

Alloplastic/synthetic graft

Several types of bone substitutes have been studied, with emphasis on synthetic materials (alloplastics), produced by chemical synthesis.

Its wide availability and the elimination of the need for a surgical procedure at a donor site represent important advantages.^{5,10}

Bioceramics has played an important role in the development of biomaterials applicable in clinical prostheses and grafts, demonstrating that artificially produced materials can be integrated into bone tissues without causing rejection.^{5,10}

Recent studies demonstrate that the release of metal ions, especially in titanium alloys and associated biomaterials, can directly influence tissue response and bone integration.¹²

Alloplastic grafts can be composed of hydroxyapatite, a naturally occurring mineral that is the main mineral component of bone, or bioactive glass... Hydroxyapatite stands out for its osteoconduction, hardness and excellent biocompatibility, and is currently the most used synthetic material.^{3,5}

Some grafts use calcium carbonate, but its use has been reduced due to rapid resorption, which can compromise bone stability. In addition, there are materials based on degradable synthetic polymers, such as polylactic acid, used alone or in combination with other components, which are gradually reabsorbed by the body.^{8,12}

Practical Applications in Dentistry

Bone grafts have wide application in modern dentistry, being used in different specialties, such as implantology, periodontics and oral surgery. Its main function is to restore the volume and integrity of bone tissue, creating suitable conditions for aesthetic and functional rehabilitation. The use of grafts aims to restore structures lost due to trauma, infection, periodontal disease or physiological resorption, ensuring better support for implants, prostheses and other restorative procedures.^{5,8}

The use of biomaterials in dentistry allows for guided tissue regeneration and the filling of bone defects with predictability and safety. Guided bone regeneration (GBR) techniques and autogenous, allogeneic, xenogeneic, and synthetic grafts are widely used according to clinical need, contributing to the formation of a stable and biocompatible bone bed. Technological advances, such as the development of personalized scaffolds and biomaterials based on hydroxyapatite and chitosan, enable less invasive and more precise approaches, promoting greater integration and predictability of results.^{8,12,13}

Among the most relevant practical applications, alveolar preservation and bone reconstitution stand out, which aim to prevent ridge resorption after tooth extraction and restore lost bone volume. Alveolar preservation, performed with biomaterials associated with membranes, maintains the morphology of the alveolus and favors natural bone regeneration, avoiding collapses that hinder future rehabilitation. Bone reconstitution, on the other hand, is indicated in cases of extensive defects or atrophies, employing combinations of grafts and regenerative techniques to restore threedimensional anatomy and allowing the correct positioning of implants.^{3,8,13}

Thus, the use of bone grafts represents one of the most effective strategies in contemporary regenerative dentistry. Its practical application ranges from the treatment of small bone losses to complex reconstructions, consolidating itself as an essential tool for the success of oral rehabilitation and for the maintenance of bone health in the long term.

DISCUSSION

With the variety of types of grafts and their various applications in dentistry, autogenous grafts are often seen as the best option, due to their low rejection rate and high compatibility with the body, which favors healing and tissue integration.^{1,2,3} However, it is important to consider that, in patients with low bone availability or contraindications for the removal of donor material, other alternatives may be indicated. The use of synthetic grafts, biomaterials, and guided bone regeneration techniques have been shown to be effective in specific situations, reducing surgical time and morbidity.^{4,5,6} In these cases, xenogenous grafts — derived from tissues of animal origin — represent a viable alternative, especially due to its wide availability and

elimination of the need for a second surgical site, with predictable clinical results.^{4,7,8} Alternatives such as the use of synthetic grafts, biological materials, or even techniques such as guided bone regeneration may be more appropriate, depending on the severity of the patient's condition, the location of the lesion, and the specific clinical conditions. The choice of the ideal treatment should take into account a detailed evaluation of the case, considering both the benefits and risks of each approach, always seeking the best option to ensure the patient's health and recovery.

A relevant aspect of the use of bone grafts is their application in implantology procedures, which are often necessary to reestablish the bone base in cases of alveolar resorption due to tooth loss. Bone resorption can result in insufficient volume for proper implant placement, making grafting an essential step to restore bone structure.¹ In these cases, the xenogenous graft presents itself as a viable alternative to the autogenous one, mainly due to its wide availability, biocompatibility, and elimination of the need for a second surgical site.^{4,6,9}

In addition, its practicality and the available volume make it an attractive option, especially when treatment time is a critical factor.³ Although the survival rate of implant rehabilitations is currently considered quite high, there is a constant effort to improve the long-term success of implant rehabilitations and minimize the risks of complications during the healing process. This is especially important in situations that require bone regeneration, as the predictability and stability of the regenerated bone are critical to successful rehabilitation.⁵ Brazilian clinical results confirm the high success rate of grafts in alveolar reconstruction, reinforcing their predictability and applicability in implant rehabilitation.¹¹

Another important point to consider is technological innovation in the field of tissue engineering. With the advancement of 3D printing techniques and the development of scaffolds (structures that support cell growth), it is possible to create customized solutions that meet the specific needs of each patient. These innovative approaches have the potential to further improve graft outcomes by promoting more effective and faster bone regeneration. Additionally, customizing grafts can lead to improved aesthetic and functional outcomes, increasing patient satisfaction.⁴

Therefore, understanding the characteristics and applications of each type of graft is essential for choosing the most appropriate method in each clinical situation. Careful selection of graft type can directly impact treatment effectiveness, patient recovery, and ultimately analysis, the success of the surgical procedure. Thus, careful evaluation of the available options, together with the personalized approach, is essential to optimize outcomes and ensure the health and well-being of patients. Thorough surgical planning and multidisciplinary collaboration among healthcare professionals are also crucial to ensure that each patient receives the treatment that is best suited to their individual needs.

CONCLUSION

The use of bone grafts in dentistry has broad applicability, encompassing various techniques, materials, and protocols aimed at restoring both function and aesthetics of the maxillofacial complex. Although autogenous grafts remain the gold standard due to their osteogenic, osteoinductive, and osteoconductive properties, the literature demonstrates that allogeneic, xenogeneic, and synthetic biomaterials can achieve comparable clinical outcomes in implant rehabilitation when properly indicated. Therefore, no single graft material can be universally considered superior. The selection of the graft type should be individualized, taking into account the extent of the bone defect, systemic conditions, availability of autogenous tissue, surgical morbidity, and rehabilitation objectives. When associated with regenerative techniques such as guided bone regeneration, these materials have demonstrated predictable and safe results, contributing to reduced treatment time and high clinical success rates.

Data Availability Statement: This study is an integrative literature review. All data analyzed were obtained from previously published studies and are properly cited in this article. No primary data were generated.

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